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Geographic Research and Teaching in India : A Disconnect with the Reality

Surya Kant*

Abstract : *The paper attempts an assessment of geographic research and teaching in India on the basis of the review of existing literature. It begins with an overview of the state of geographic research and teaching in the world as a whole with focus on English speaking world followed by a detailed study of the Indian scenario. The paper noted a huge disconnect between the ground realities and the research and teaching of geography in India. There is not only a crisis of identity but also a lack of contemporary relevance in our researches and teaching courses. Finally, the paper recommended some remedial measures to overcome the problem and strengthen the roots of our discipline.*

Key Words: *regionalism, regional backwardness, re-inventing regional geography, paradigm shift, identity crisis*

Contemporary India and Geographic Research

The last quarter of the 20th century was a highly eventful period for India. The country witnessed remarkable changes of profound social, economic, political, environmental and spatial implications. Following the implementation of the Backward Classes Commission Report (popularly known as Mandal Commission) in 1990 and the emergence of caste and region based politics and political parties on the political horizon coinciding with a decline of the Indian National Congress set the stage for casteism and regionalism in India's democratic politics. In June 1991, India adopted a new economic policy setting the stage for liberalization, privatization and globalization of Indian economy, a move to liberate Indian economy from the Stateism for making it market friendly. In 1992, Indian Parliament passed the two Acts, *Panchayati Raj Act* and *Nagarpalika Act*, to strengthen democracy and development at the grass-root level; setting the stage for the participatory development, where millions of democratically elected members of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) at the village, development block and district levels in rural areas and of Urban Local Bodies at the level of towns, cities and the metropolitan centres were supposed to guide the fate of the development with their active involvement in decision-making at the grass-root level.

The process of change/reforms in socio-economic environment of the country continued even during the 21st century. Several new Acts, such as Right to Information (RTI) in 2005, Right to Education (RTE) Act in 2009, and the National Food Security Act (popularly known Right to Food

* Formerly Professor, Department of Geography, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160014, email : surya.kant1949@gmail.com

Bill) in 2013 were enacted by the Indian Parliament to make the government functioning more transparent, create general awareness among all the citizens and make life of the poor and the needy healthy and livable.

On one hand, the penetration of caste identity based regionalism in India's democratic politics posed a variety of problems and challenges before the federalism and nationalism in the country. On the other, growth oriented policies initiated under the new economic policy regime posed a serious threat to environment and ecology especially in mineral rich tribal areas and big urban-industrial complex owing to reckless exploitation of natural resources and haphazard urban-industrial development along with widening of inter-personal, inter-regional and intra-regional inequalities in development. At the same time, labour migration from backward regions to big metropolitan cities in search of job opportunities set the stage for further slumming and haphazard growth of Indian metropolises.

As a policy intervention, Government of India undertook several measures to correct the situation. Hundreds of new programmes were initiated or existing ones re-structured with the intent to check environmental degradation, increase income and generate employment, build urban infrastructure, narrow down social, regional and intra-regional inequalities, safe guard the interests of minorities, backward castes, scheduled castes and tribals, ensure food security, provide rural sanitation and safe drinking water supply and so on. Some of the ambitious programmes in this category include Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (education for all), National Rural Health Mission, Integrated Child Development Services, Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme, Pradhan Mantri Gram Sarak Yojana, Mid-Day Meal Scheme, Backward Regions Grant Fund and Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission. In addition, the Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-2017) placed before itself a challenging task of *attaining a faster, more inclusive and sustainable growth*. In other words, the Plan proposed a growth target of 8.0 per cent with commitment to make it environmentally sustainable and socially and geographically equitable. Development and conservation of land and water resources along with regionally equitable development were at the core of its high growth agenda for the next five years (Government of India, 2013). Further, following General Elections to the sixteenth Lok Sabha, the new government under Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi, taking over the reigns in the last week of May 2014, initiated a new programmes such as, Make in India, Smart City, Starts Up, Skill Development, so as to generate employment for the youth in India by making India an attractive investment hub for the foreign investors. What to manufacture and where to manufacture come as an immediate query in one's mind with regard to Make in India program.

Earlier, the opening up of Indian economy to market forces in 1991 placed the Indian middle class in prominence for its propensity to benefit from the new economic policies. Differently estimated, its size is between 350 and 450 million persons, projected to 583 million by 2025 (McKinsey Global Institute quoted in Varma, 2007), considered as a remarkable change in Indian society with attendant socio-economic implications. On the other hand, the share of population living below

poverty in the country has though declined in post-reforms period but got regionally concentrated in economically backward and highly urban-industrial states (Kant, 2002)

Notably, all the issues and problems referred to in the preceding paragraphs are geographical in nature. May it be the question of federalism, nationalism, globalization and privatization of economy, decentralization of democracy and development, ethnicity based regionalism in politics, resource degradation and environmental pollution, climate change, land transformation, slumming of metropolitan cities, regional and intra-regional inequalities in development, foreign direct investment in Indian manufacturing industry, spatial distribution and demographic dynamism of Indian middle class, and making development (environmentally, socially and spatially) sustainable and equitable in India, all have geographical dimensions and hence need geographical treatment for their comprehensive handling and seeking durable solution. Unfortunately, however, Indian geography has shown little research interest in such issues and problems during the last six decades of independence in India.

Paradigmatic Changes in Geography

On the other side of the scale, discipline of geography especially human geography also experienced sweeping changes in its philosophy, methodology and practice, particularly after the 1980s. Indian geography was not immune to all such changes. On the theoretical plane, realism, post-structuralism, postmodernism and gender and feminism overpowered positivism, humanism, behaviouralism, welfarism, and structuralism. Methodologically, new techniques such as satellite imagery, GIS and GPS started replacing traditional tools, including cartographic mapping, topographic maps, and field surveying. Side by side, research took problem-oriented or applied turn, away from the traditional disciplinary boundaries. With applied orientation in research, often reflecting the requirements of funding agencies rather than the traditional mode of university level research disciplines, the traditional disciplinary boundaries started blurring in the University system. Consequently, a new and interdisciplinary job market took shape, as the number of traditional discipline oriented posts, especially teaching posts did not increase sufficiently both at the university/college and the school levels.

The planning organizations now advertise posts that do not require training in any specific disciplines; and the teaching posts at the higher and school levels are either frizzed or not filled. All this has placed a tremendous pressure on discipline-oriented structure of the universities to move in the direction of reorienting their teaching courses to suit the new job market requirements, and the research to fulfil the needs of business and industry. The discipline of Geography in India is under a tremendous pressure to reorient its teaching and research following the almost stagnant situation in its traditional job market in teaching (school and university levels) and middle level government jobs. In fact, geographers are mainly employed in teaching in this country. According to a rough estimate nearly nine of each ten geographers in India are in teaching (Kapur, 2000). The same may be more or less true of other academic disciplines too. Restructuring of teaching courses by lifting contents in the syllabi and introducing the new Master's/diploma courses in remote sensing and geographical information systems, and even in disaster management by several

Geography Departments in Indian universities are some of the ongoing effortstried in India and some other countries. The main objective is to provide the market orientation to the discipline.

The Objective

This paper is a candid attent to examine the current disconnect between geographic teaching and research, on one hand, and the national mood in India, on the other. Geographic community in India, as a whole, owes some social responsibility to the nation. To begin with, an attempt will be made to assess the state of geography in the world with a focus on English speaking world, followed by an examination of current state of Indian geography, and finally to suggest a few new research themes,reflecting the needs the 21st century India. Keeping in view the time required for conducting empirical study on teaching and research in Indian geography, the paper will heavily depend on observations/comments made in such kind of reviews undertaken earlier by several scholars and available in the existing literature including the books/journals published in English language.

Teaching and Research in Geography: An Overview

A. In General

In a book entitled ‘What is Geography?’, (Bonnett 2008) termed geography ‘a fundamental fascination’, whose death has been predicted, even announced many times in last 100 years or so, ‘but it refuses to die’.). To him, ‘Geography is not a specialism, like sociology or geology. Nor is it the product only of recent history. Geography, like history, is an infuriating but vital combination of the modern and pre-modern. Its ambition is absurdly vast. But we know it would be more absurd to abandon it. Geography has become the international discipline, with an agenda that reflects the development of a global, commercial civilization.... geography’s modern role exposes deep-seated dilemmas and ambiguities, problems that revolve around the imbalance of power between different parts of the world’.

Phil Hubbard *et. al.* (2002), in the *Preface* to their recent book entitled “Thinking Geographically”,while sharing their experiences as university teachers, made two interconnected observations: (i) the majority of undergraduate geography students have an aversion to studying theory and do not understand/appreciate its importance. They feel happy with the ‘facts’ about the world, rather than approaching and comprehending ideas about the way world works. In other words, students prefer the observable world in place of an abstract world of ideas and propositions; and (ii) encouraging students to ‘think geographically’is often difficult and thankless task, made all the more arduous by the lack of accessible texts that spell out clearly to students the *value* of theory and why they should (and need to) engage with it. A general approach to write texts of theory is only in the abstract, fastidiously cataloguing the history of different schools of thought,but rarely showing how such ideas impinge on the practice of creating geographical knowledge.

Though the authors wanted to justify the title and the contents of book written by them, but it brought home clearly the following messages: (a) geography students at the undergraduate level are more interested in the empirical rather than theoretical knowledge of the way real world works;

and (b) there is a dearth of text books especially on geographic thought, emphasizing on the value of theory and why a student should engage with it.

Thrift (2002), while reclaiming the future of geography, begins with an optimistic statement, 'the times are on our side: things are becoming more geographical'. Then he narrated the success stories of geographic research, both in physical and human geography, and claimed that we must feel proud of achievements. To him, human geography's intervention in public policy goes beyond just advising government and business. There is now a complete involvement in the public realm as a whole. Focusing on the increasing relevance of geography in resolving to the real world problems, he remarked that not everything in the garden of geography is entirely rosy. He identified the four major problems engulfing the geography: (i) moving of human and physical geography in divergent directions to make common zones of understanding a rare opportunity; (ii) lack of ambition and general un-adventurousness, resulting in weakening of the benefits accruing from interdisciplinary interactions and thus keeping busy with histories of the discipline, circulated through the same old conferences and 'thereby generally confirming geography's presence as themselves; (iii) a general decline in the production of learned books and monographs in favour of journal articles, leading to complete dearth of bestseller books by the geographers unlike the historians and scientists, who regularly top non-fiction bestseller lists and do an invaluable job in popularizing those pursuits; and (iv) keeping geography buoyant in the schools, leaving school geography in several countries in a fairly ragged state. It has been diluted by environmental studies or has to compete with other disciplines like history for the same slot. He cautioned that 'without producing geography in schools, there will be no geography'. Finally, he advised to maintain the intellectual integrity of geography consistently, so as to produce knowledge at the cutting-edge of developments in the sciences, social sciences and humanities, on one hand, and enhance the employability of geographers, on the other. He stated that future of geography lies upon in making geography central, intellectually and practically both, to the world we live in.

In response to Nigel Thrift's views on 'the Future of Geography', Clefford (2002) expressed his reservations at presenting a somewhat rosy picture of the future of geography by Thrift and asserted that within geography, the ever-increasing diversity of its subject matter and research philosophy poses problems for disciplinary identity, reflected in the more restricted perspective of the subject outside the universities. He added that things are getting further compounded by a weakening of the link between geography in the universities and the schools. He was for giving a serious attention to the changing nature of the discipline, its positioning with respect to other subjects, and its relations with the wider world. Finally, he was hopeful 'that geography can (and should) still prosper', but added that 'the more positive outcome will depend upon 'an appreciation and nurturing of a more traditional geographical heritage ... as well as a more creative view of the relationship between fundamental and applied research'.

Johnston (2003), entering the debate about the inter-relationships between human and physical geography and their different research and publication practices, analyzed all publications submitted by United Kingdoms geographers to the 2001 Research Assessment Exercise (RAE). After a detailed

analysis of 23 research journals having majority of published papers by geographers, he found a substantial difference between human and physical geographers in their publication strategies-majority of physical geographers placing their papers in multi-disciplinary journals (hydrology and quaternary studies), where geographers making a minority participants and their authors seeking peer approval outside their institutionalized discipline, against this the majority of human geographers publishing 'their best work in journals aimed mainly at geographers alone'. In other words, 'human geographers largely talk among themselves, it seems, while physical geographers prefer to talk to colleagues in other disciplines'. A comparison with other disciplines, in the earth and environmental and social sciences, also indicates differences between geographers and their peers. 'The high impact science journals only occasionally carry papers by geographers'. However, 'physical geographers are more scientifically extrovert than their counterparts in human geography. But human geographers are not entirely isolated: many of their publications have bibliographies that range widely across the social sciences, so that at least some of their papers and books are connecting their discipline to wider intellectual currents. In addition, human geographers, though introvert, are 'less parochial than their colleagues in either sociology or political science' (Johnston, 2003). Finally, Johnston states, 'geography in the UK is not an exemplar of the paradigm academic discipline, comprising a community occupying and defending a well-defined intellectual territory. It is a whole comprising range of parts pulling in different directions-something that the data presented here suggest, marks it out as substantially different from some of its neighbouring disciplines, especially in the social sciences. That may be a strength-but probably only a strength if the body is carefully managed'.

B. In Indian Universities

Turning now to geographic research and teaching in India, the historical roots of geography goes back to ancient times (Das, 1894; Ali, 1966; Dubey, 1967; Mukerji, 1969; Karan, 1992). It was, however, formally introduced during the British rule in India. Writing on evolution and growth of the discipline of geography in India, Kapur (2002) stated that geographical studies acquired applied value in the institutes set up by the British in the early 19th century, but the concern for the discipline of geography did not crystallize till the 20th century. This could happen in spite of the fact that the British used well the tools of geography to measure, collect, organize and document the geographical facts of India. It is precisely the mid-1920s when the discipline of geography institutionalized in India: first geographical associations formed and then its teaching at undergraduate level started in colleges affiliated to Lahore, Aligarh, and Patna universities. Passing through various difficult phases, the academic success in geography evolved slowly.

This formative phase of colonial period, the main thrust remaining on accumulation of the gazetteer type understanding on India for administrative and resource utilization purposes rather than on learning the basics of the discipline, was followed by a phase of physical expansion and disciplinary specialization during the post-independence period. Spanning over about three decades during 1950-1980, this period witnessed opening of unparalleled opportunities for geographers in its entire history in India. But, unlike economists and sociologists, the geographers failed to make

their mark on the national scene. By the closing years of the 20th century, the general impression was that despite the good times geographers in India had failed to deliver the desired goals to either academics or national development (Kapur, 2002). Even during their best times, 1950s to mid-1970s, geographers failed to create centres, which could endure or display their works. Even now, 'the citadels of specialization are seen as dwarfed in quality though more diversified in complexion of research and teaching' (Krishan, 2002).

The post-1980 phase may, thus, be termed as a phase of diversification in the complexion of teaching and research in Indian geography but decline in quality of teaching and research both. It was during this period that three most exciting, hard hitting and somewhat controversial articles, on the state of Indian geography, were written by A.B. Mukerji (1991), R.D. Dikshit (2001), and Anu Kapur (2004).

Mukerji blamed Indian Geography for selection of hybrid variety of research themes not very much suited to indigenous situation and developing regional research foci, functioning like fiefdoms, without much interaction and exchange from national perspective. He underlined 'missing methodology', 'fizzling physical geography', 'sterile stereotypes', 'feeble fieldwork', and 'intellectual neocolonisation' as the main banes of the discipline of geography in India. Finally, he wanted Indian geography to be more human and humane, and characteristically Indian. In the view of Dikshit, Indian geography is almost stagnant for the last thirty years, with some exceptions. To him, our teaching and research has 'failed to catch up with the rapid pace of the overall development in the philosophy and methodology of geography. Also, he criticized the discipline of geography in India for paying little attention to the students' training in disciplinary structure. He lamented for keeping course on geographic thought, which were essentially structured in the style of Dickinson's *Makers of Modern Geography* having greater focus on the makers than the things made... the narrative seldom going beyond the so-called quantitative revolution, leaving an all-round illiteracy in respect of the post-1970 developments in geographical theory. He lamented for giving superficial attention to the teaching of physical geography in India to the extent of geography losing its identity as an environmental science. Finally, he called for a surgical operation at every level of Indian geography, and felt the need to train students in theory and methodology of geography on priority basis. Armed with facts and figures, Kapur finds Geography in India lagging far behind the other social sciences in terms of teaching, research, and professionalism. She termed Indian geography 'a languishing social science'. Raising a number of questions relating to weak or marginalized position of geography within the social sciences in India, perception about the teaching and research in geography, relative absence of geographers from social science institutes, and geographers' inability to establish their credentials as social scientist, she went on to explain the reasons behind all this. She stated that environmentalism being at its core and dualism between physical geography and human geography might have given a perception that geography is study of places and the geographer is primarily an explorer, traveller, map maker, and is distantly located from the arena of social sciences. She was, however, quick to add that 'this blurred perception could easily be altered if geographers had fostered an active interaction with social sciences and demonstrated that the 'earth' is not a mere physical entity but essentially a 'home of humankind'. She was pained to

observe that geographers are hardly visible in social science research institutes or contributing to issues on public policy. She lamented a hesitant alliance 'between geography and public policy in India'; hijacking of the near exclusive domains of geography by others; and lack of geographical studies themes such as natural hazards, disasters, administrative/political reorganization of space in the country. In addition, she was quite harsh in her comments on the quality of geographic research in India. To her 'it is difficult to find Indian geographers who have made a marked impression even regionally, let alone globally on the expansion of ideas, theory and knowledge relating to their discipline.most publications by geographers have gained very little in terms of attracting reviews or attention from other social scientists'. She opined that the geographers in India are too complacent, even to undertake a diagnosis of their malady; and may be the reason for their marginal position within the social sciences. She blamed geographers in India for adamantly avoiding the spotlight on them, and warned them for their further marginalization by other social sciences because charity begins at home. Finally, she believes that geography in India has not only a bright future but also inherent potential to lead other social sciences, but for that 'there is need to reinvent our commitment'.

Her paper generated heat and widespread debate and discussions in Geography. Even in the *Economic and Political Weekly*, where she published the paper, three short discussions appeared (Prasad, 2005; Lahiri-Dutt, 2005 and Landy, 2005). Prasad, while supporting Kapur's view, termed geographic teaching in higher education of India more a north Indian, rural, non-metropolitan and regional level phenomenon. She was of the view that the newly established Central universities in India have almost completely ignored the discipline of geography; and there was a lack of contextualization in teaching and research of geography in India. Lahiri-Dutt, while sharing personal experiences gained during the two decades teaching at University of Burdwan (West Bengal) lamented for the lack of infrastructure including laboratory and library facilities for both the students and teachers in state universities, outdated school level curriculum leading to mediocre students joining geography at undergraduate level, and lopsided career development. To her, it is the geographer's self-image that carries more weight than how others view a geographer. Therefore, the need of the hour is to ponder the question: why are not other academics, the non-geographers, aware that geography does matter? Landy, a French geographer participating in the discussion, stated that the situation is not much different in France. Geography is not among popular subjects in his country, few students get enrolled and fewer books published. Landy opines that 'we hardly use all the potential of geography', hence the geographers are also to be blamed for the current state of our discipline. To him 'doing geography is a proof that we do know; that we are consequently either blind or cowards, if we do not commit ourselves to making a better world'.

Earlier in 1998, The National Association of Geographers, India (NAGI) set a number of Task Forces under the Chairmanship of Professor H.N.Sharma, Guhawati University, Guhawati (Assam). Documents produced by these Task Forces were published in *Annals of NAGI* (Volume 20, June 2000). Four reports (Dhabriya; Krishan; Sharma; Kapur) make interesting and thought provoking reading. Krishan's report, Indian Geography: Tasks Ahead, presents an overview of progress reports of Indian geography prepared by eminent geographers along with an examination of essential messages emerging out of the 'presidential addresses', delivered at the annual conferences of the

NAGI followed by suggestions on the future line of action. Some of the inferences he drew are worth producing. To him, 'Indian Geography has a great absorptive power by way of assimilating any new concepts or methodologies, however lacking innovativeness. There is more bulk than brain in our research'. Also he noted greater focus on human geography at the cost of physical geography and serious lack of training in research methodology, resulting in poor research quality. Visualizing increased degree of complexity in coming decades of regional patterns of ecology, economy, society and polity in India, requiring higher levels of competence capacity on the part of geographers to comprehend, he opined that that Indian geography must strengthen its reflexes by way of immediately responding to new challenges. To him, the geographers in India must have a clear perspective of the spirit and purpose of their discipline; do blending of theoretical and empirical aspects of any theme under study; conduct fieldwork as distinctive characteristic, adhere to social relevance of their teaching and research, improve their visibility and presence at all levels, and concentrate on those dimensions of their discipline, where they have greater competence. He opined that Indian geography must have its own identity, must shift to 'spatial integration' from 'spatial differentiation' paradigm, explore new research themes, and look towards the demand side of their discipline in place of supply side. To him, the 'quality of Indian Geography is contingent upon the quality of teaching and research in our discipline'. He recommended for having a reconstruction plan for Indian geography, where in each of the three stakeholders-the captains, the initiates and the system holding something. In view of their experiences and effectiveness, the *captains* shouldering greater responsibility, *the initiates* keeping them highly motivated and strong pressure builders to reform the discipline on regular basis, and *the system* recognizing the virtues and relevance of the discipline. To him, improving of our visibility at all levels is the secret of success to achieve all this.

Some of the concerns of Krishan have been echoed elsewhere too. While delivering his Presidential address to the 10th NAGI Congress in 1988, Professor Satyesh Chakraborty categorically stated, 'The way we have developed our expertise in science would not let us respond to all the facets of the problematique with equal competence. It would be foolish to think otherwise....I should therefore, request you to examine and select the specific facet where we can engage ourselves, without sacrificing the rigour of our discipline'. Dikshit (1995) warned against the neglect of physical geography and Singh (2012) advocated for making geographic research relevant to contemporary social issues to make our discipline successful.

Writing on development of Indian geography, Noble (2004), an American geographer with keen interest in Indian geography, noted the inbreeding as one of the most serious problems facing the geography departments in India. To him, hiring of their own graduates for teaching, a wide spread practice of Indian geography, is stifling the independent thought, encouraging provincialism and fostering inbreeding- inhibiting the cross-fertilization likely to be generated by the introduction of diversity of opinion and training. In another interesting observation, he noted that soon after independence in 1947 developmental issues such as scarce resources, widespread poverty and competing and conflicting demands were teething problems of India, but 'beginning in 1955, urban geography came to occupy a steadily more important segment of all geographic enquiry', the main

hub of urban studies being the Department of Geography, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi under the leadership of R.L.Singh. However, a look at the regional setting of Varanasi in those days indicate to rural poverty, low agricultural productivity, water resource management, and underdevelopment- the major concerns needing immediate attention of planners, policy-makers and the academicians too. Thus, the geographic community and its leadership failing to gauge the regional mood and contribute to identification and comprehensive analysis of such problems at regional and local scales. Urban geography gradually spread over to other parts of India to become a popular teaching and research sub-field. Unfortunately, however, there is hardly any standard and comprehensive text book on urban geography by an Indian geographer. Department of Geography, Panjab University at Chandigarh is yet another example of such kind. Here 'population geography', another sub-field of geography, took its roots in late 1960s, progressed and spread to other parts of India. However, the rural and agricultural development, ecological implications of green revolution, border area development, and displacement induced due to partition and hydel projects were some of the major developmental issues and concerns of the region. No teaching course till date is offered on rural development at this department and standard book on population geography came in late 1980s and the teaching and research in population geography has remained confined mainly to distribution, density, and demographic attributes of population. Population-Environment-Development Interface has remained the least explored research theme. Given the agricultural and rural background of western Uttar Pradesh, agricultural land use studies in agricultural geography at Department of Geography, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh was perhaps the better proposition at that time. But the role of government policy in changing the agricultural land use and vice versa remained the least explored dimension in such studies. Obviously, the three major schools of geography located in north Indian plains failed to capture the regional realities of their surroundings, remaining thus divorced from issues and problems of immediate attention.

Nevertheless, the objective assessment of Indian geography suggested that today it stands more diversified in teaching and research both. This might be the outcome of the pressure created due to the churning within the discipline, crystallizing over the period. The publication of *Voice of Concern* in 2000 followed by that of NAGI's Tasks Force Reports in the *Annals of NAGI* in the same year, publication of the paper 'Geography in India: A Languishing Social Science' in *Economic and Political Weekly* in 2004, and organization of National Workshops by the Pune based *Indian Institute of Geographers* on Reorienting Indian Geography at the University and College levels held at Thiruvananthapuram in 2011, at Burdwan in 2013, at New Delhi in 2014 and at Pune in 2014. New courses on remote sensing and geographic information systems, geographic philosophy and methodology, environmental studies, disaster management, water sources, resource management, sustainability, population and development, and so on have been started by the several university departments. In addition, research domain has also enlarged to include themes on urban land transformation, urban-rural relations, social and physical vulnerability, border area development, food security, status of women, disasters and development, displacement and development, urban slums, public policy and administration, resource degradation and environmental pollution. Side by side, the use of remote and geographical information systems (GIS) has brought physical and human geographies closer to each other.

Unfortunately, however, the component of field work is on decline. Even the students studying courses on geomorphology and remote sensing are not frequently taken to the field for verification—an essential ingredient of image processing and interpretation. Map reading habit among the students and teachers is on the decline, the same is true of the use of maps for research and teaching. Availability of infrastructure required for teaching courses such as remote sensing, GIS and GPS is severely lacking in several university departments. Course on air photo interpretation is taught without the requisite pair of photographs and the several students do not know how to open a stereoscope to make three dimensional images. Courses on remote sensing and GIS are taught with pirated versions of software. Even the departments, claiming to offer Master's degree courses in remote sensing and GIS, have only a few faculty members who are fully equipped to handle or work with GIS software. Our visibility at the national and regional levels is poor. Hardly any geographer is invited for delivering inaugural address to any conference attended by the scholars and academicians from the social sciences or invited to chair or be a member of national or regional level committees or expert groups formed to discuss and report on important government policy or programme related issues.

In brief, the reviews and views presented in the preceding paragraphs make it evidently clear that several of the weaknesses or problems with teaching and research of Indian geography, noticed today, are not confined/specific to Indian geography, some are common to all parts of the world. Secondly, these have been pointed out time and again along with remedial measures to overcome. It seems that problem lies with soul searching and translating the ideas into realities. Here, one is tempted to raise some questions: How serious the different Presidents of NAGI have been to translate into the reality the ideas or plans they visualized/articulated in their Presidential addresses? How serious we are to produce standard text books on different branches of geography, conduct fieldwork based studies, conduct policy oriented or applied researches, do innovative teaching and research, update our curriculum on a regular basis and getting good faculty members, trained in foreign universities, on our staff? Further, how many of us are ready to go to schools to teach and interact with geography teachers and students there? Now, I would like to share some of my personal experiences of teaching and research in geography.

Observations based on Personal Experiences

As a faculty, I joined Panjab University, Chandigarh in 1988. In 1989, the Board of Studies in Geography met for updating the syllabus for PG classes and to appoint the examiners. Keeping in view the interests of the students appearing for competitive examinations, the then chairperson favoured to incorporate the contents from the syllabus prescribed for competitive examinations, especially the civil services examination conducted by the Union Public Service Commission (UPSC), New Delhi. Some of the contents of the UPSC syllabus was incorporated in the existing papers. Some new courses were also framed and passed by the Board. However, it all happened not without a tough opposition from the Board's member belonging to the PG department of geography in an affiliated college. As a result, newly introduced course were designated as the optional courses.

By implication, the students those aspiring to appear in competitive examinations but studying Geography in the affiliated college were denied the benefit of the newly introduced courses.

Later on, it came to my notice that it is a standard practice not only in this part but also in other parts of the country. In this way, in case of several Indian universities, having a large number of PG departments of geography in the affiliated colleges, the benefits of new courses introduced with a view to apprise students with contemporary or emerging trends in teaching and or research of geography, do not percolate down to the level of the students studying in colleges located in small towns. It means those on the margin get further marginalized. There are several Indian universities, where the number of affiliated colleges teaching PG courses is quite large.

It is, however, interesting and amusing to learn from the different sources that sometimes the new courses are framed and introduced to accommodate the privileged ones having the blessings of important authorities/department heads. The most common argument advanced to justify such appointments is that the appointed faculty is specializing in the most contemporary and/or applied subfield of our discipline, a need of the hour. Notwithstanding the argued importance of such new courses, these are closed down soon after that privileged person moves to other post/place. In contrast, the long running courses are closed down with the retirement of a particular faculty member. I personally know, a course on Mathematical Geography, running in a university department, was struck out of the syllabus soon after the retirement of a teacher teaching the course for a very long period. The reliable sources indicates that someone of his colleagues feared that he may be called as a guest faculty to teach that popular course. It means the plans and the strategies are framed/reframed and implemented/re-oriented to promote or demote individuals rather than the interests of the discipline.

Another experience relates to my appointment as an external examiner to conduct the practical examination of 'Remote Sensing and Aerial Photo-Interpretation' at a PG department of geography, affiliated to Meerut University, Meerut. There were nearly eighty students to undertake the examination, against a few pairs of aerial photographs available with the department, and there was hardly any satellite images. During viva voce, several students admitted that they have seen the aerial photographs and pocket stereoscopes for the first time, and only a few could open the pocket stereoscope correctly. My surprise heightened to touch its climax, when the senior most faculty member there asked me to award a minimum 80.0 per cent to students appearing in that practical examination.

Yet another experience relates to evaluation of doctoral research degrees in geography, submitted to different Indian universities. I received three theses from a particular university, submitted under one supervisor and all on one district, as the study area, studying its (i) forest resources, (ii) water resources and (iii) rural service centres. Roughly forty per cent of the material in all the three theses was nearly the same. Revision and resubmission were the recommendations on all the three, but none came back to me for revaluation. Another thesis, referred to me as the third examiner, was also recommended for revision and re-submission. It came back to me after the

revision and re-submission. To my utter surprise, revised and re-submitted thesis had hardly any change/modification, on the suggested lines.

The motive behind mentioning all such incidents is that it involves not only the credibility of the researchers but also of research supervisors, and that of the system. In fact, the evaluation, an integral part of both teaching and research in any discipline, needs our priority attention, especially of those in senior positions, so that a clear cut message reach to all the concerned persons that the quality will never be compromised, may it be evaluation of teaching or research in geography.

The Task Ahead

We have to reinvent the Indian Geography. For this, we need to prepare a roadmap assigning our topmost priority to the following:-

1. **Taking care of identity crisis and the blurred image of Indian Geography:** Indian geography is blamed for the lack of own identity. It is considered replica of Western geography, not properly rooted in Indian soils. Early leadership, trained in western universities, is generally blamed for this.

Indian geography must have its own identity. But, we need to define the question of identity in terms of its form and structure. Do we mean that Indian geography be identified by its independent philosophy or methodology or research themes. Krishan (2000) suggested that Indian geography must get inspirations from Indian philosophy, which is integrating in nature, always looking for the unity in diversity. In my view, we can establish independent identity of Indian geography by investigating research themes and teaching issues and problems, which are deeply rooted in our social, economic, political, and environmental and ecological settings, reflecting contemporary concerns in the historical context.

Secondly, the popular image of geography is far different and divorced from the one held by its practitioners. The popular image of geography is that a geographer knows about places, mountains, rivers, and weather and the climate. Also, the general masses feel that geography is a school level subject, and has nothing to do with higher education. Against this, the practitioners of geography strong feel that their discipline is capable of solving a variety of complex national, regional and local problems. Today, a geographer in India is considered like a doctor, who considers him/her a heart specialists but people come to his/her clinic for consulting only for common ailments like cough and cold. We need to find out a solution for this image gap. We need to change our strategy to place out crafts in the demand mode from the current supply mode. In other words, we have to learn, through mutual interaction with the common man and the administrator, what they expect from us rather than what we can provide to them?

2. **Exploring the new research and teaching themes:** We need to explore new themes for research keeping in view their contemporary relevance to people, administrators and the

law-makers of the country. Already laudable efforts have been made to draw our attention (Kapur, 2002; Krishan, 2000; Krishan, 2013). To me, themes such as land transformation in and around our metropolitan cities, residential mobility within and around the big cities, mapping of territorial administration organized by different kind of urban service like health, education, water supply, electricity supply, and sewerage in metropolitan areas, study of demographic and socio-economic characteristics of parliamentary and assembly constituencies, nature of association between democracy and development, ecological and environmental fall outs of big development projects, development induced displacement, spatial impact of globalization on local economy, demographic and socio-economic characteristics of Indian Middle class and the role of the Middle Class in development and democracy, mapping and management of sustainable development at different hierarchical scales, measurement of degree of efficiency/inefficiency of territorial administration in different regions/states of India, development and disasters, and climate change must get our highest priority.

3. **Pro-poor Cartography:** Cartography has always been an important methodological tool with the geographers. We must use cartography to articulate and highlight the issues and problems faced by the marginalized and poor social groups (such as slum dwellers, forest dwellers, displaced and houseless population, unemployed, child workers, sex workers, street vendors, rickshaw pullers, beggars and so on) and marginal areas/region (such as hill, coastal, drought prone, desert, flood prone, degraded, waterlogged, industrially/economically depressed or lagging areas). We can also prepare city guide maps along with maps required to the administrators for administrative purpose.
4. **Writing of Standard Text Books:** There is a dearth of standard text books written by Indian geographers. As a result, both the teachers and the students are forced to read books written by foreign authors, almost completely devoid of Indian examples and illustrations, always referring to alien situations. Due to the contextual gap, our students fail to find interest and link with the themes or issues discussed in these books. Moreover, the books authored by foreign scholars are quite expensive, so out of the reach of our students; hence depending on sub-standard quality of material. No doubt, some efforts have been made in this direction in the recent years, but there is a need to accelerate our efforts in the years to come. Geographic Associations, such as The National Association of Geographers of India and The Institute of Indian Geographers can provide institutional support to the authors coming forward to write such books.
5. **Promotion of Regional Studies:** We need to re-invent regional studies. We must address questions such as: What has been the contribution of different regions of India to national development in the past and present? (ii) What shall be development scenario of a particular region and problems related to development in the next 15 to 20 years? This will require us to master over forecasting techniques. Also, we have to develop regional expertise to the

extent that our colleagues are consulted by the planners and policy-makers, while development preparing plans for such regions.

- 6. Attracting Good Students to Geography:** Quality of teaching and research in any academic discipline is highly contingent upon the quality of students it attract and the way trained them. The good students joins a subject only when they find good future prospects. We need to grab the emerging opportunities and strengthen the existing ones to assure the students joining geography courses at different levels. We need to improve our marketability, the senior geographers playing an important role.

In the end, I am optimistic that geography and geographers have a better future in this country.

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